

WAYS TO IMPROVE MARKETING ACTIVITIES AT UZMETKOMBINAT JSC

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Abstract. *In this article, marketing activities in the company are mainly focused on developing interaction with customers, establishing relationships with the brand, selling products and services, improving relations with customers and creating a safe and simple communication environment with communication intentions mastered by the company, social media and digital marketing.*

Key words: *Enterprise, customer, ferrous metallurgy, communication, industry, competition, technology.*

Annotatsiya. *Mazkur maqolada korxonada marketing faoliyati asosan mijozlar bilan o'zaro munosabatni rivojlantirish, brend bilan munosabatlarni o'rnatish, mahsulotlar va xizmatlar sotish, mijozlar bilan aloqalarni yaxshilash va kompaniya tomonidan o'zlashtirilgan kommunikatsiya niyatlari bilan xavfsizlik va sodda kommunikatsiya muhitini yaratish, ijtimoiy media va raqamli marketing ko'rib chiqilgan.*

Kalitli so'zlar: *Korxonada, mijoz, qora metallurgiya, kommunikatsiya, industriya, raqobat, texnologiya.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается маркетинговая деятельность в компании в основном направлена на развитие взаимодействия с клиентами, установление отношений с брендом, продажу продуктов и услуг, улучшение отношений с клиентами и создание безопасной и простой среды общения с коммуникационными намерениями, освоенными компанией, социальными сетями и цифровым маркетингом.*

Ключевые слова: *Предприятие, заказчик, черная металлургия, коммуникация, промышленность, конкуренция, технология.*

Introduction. The development of ferrous metallurgy in the Republic of Uzbekistan is the most important priority state task of the modern stage of economic development. Continuous reconstruction, technical re-equipment and modernization of production allows us to produce high-quality competitive products, which supply products to industrial enterprises and the construction industry of the republic, as well as export.

In accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4937 dated December 28, 2020 "On the Program for the Development of the Joint-Stock Company "Uzmetkombinat"", a large investment project "Construction of a Casting and Rolling Complex" is being implemented by the Joint-Stock Company "Uzmetkombinat". The project implementation period is 2020-2024. The "Construction of a Casting and Rolling Complex" project is the largest investment project. Based on this project, the plant will produce 1.04 million tons of import-substituting, export-oriented, hot-rolled steel sheet coils. As a result of the implementation of this project, the plant's production capacity will almost double. The world leader in the supply of

metallurgical equipment, Daniele (Italy), and the contractor Ronesanc Austria (Turkey), which has extensive international experience in the construction of industrial facilities, are cooperating in the implementation of this investment project. Currently, the construction of the Foundry and Rolling Mill is in full swing.

Analysis of literature on the topic.An analysis of the existing literature on marketing shows the need to improve modern marketing principles, brand promotion methods, and a flexible approach to consumer requirements. In his textbook on marketing strategies, the expert RGIbragimov states the following: "Marketing strategy is understood as the use of a model of the principles of an enterprise's behavior in the market, established for a certain period of time. With its help, the enterprise seeks to ensure its success." Many economists have been involved in the development and implementation of marketing strategies. Among them are such famous scientists as F. Kotler, David Aaker, Clayton Christensen, Seth Godin, Kevin Keller, Byron Sharp, and Jay Bayer.

While the research conducted in the field of marketing in our country for many years is based on national characteristics, it is also necessary to recognize the scientists who have made a significant contribution to the development of marketing theory. These include R.Ibragimov, YO.Abdullaev, A.Saliev, M.Sharifkhodjaev, D.Rakhimova, Sh.Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh.Musayeva and others..

Research methodology.The study used a systematic approach, marketing analysis, benchmarking, and digital metrics. Mass surveillance methods were used to collect and analyze data from social media platforms.

Analysis and results.Modern marketing involves new approaches to providing a better experience to customers through new strategies and approaches using different channels and technologies. It is different from traditional marketing, which is used to attract a large number of users, provide them with a specifically targeted and enjoyable experience, and build good relationships with customers.

Modern marketing offers companies a great opportunity to strengthen their relationships with customers, attract them, and offer them convenience. This helps to innovate the market through new approaches and strategies and develop successful marketing strategies for companies.

Increasing the success of the company: IMC plays an important role in increasing the success of the company, as it helps to advertise the company on its various scales by combining various communication tools and allows you to establish effective relationships with customers by properly targeting all communication tools.

IMC plays a major role in building brand awareness and building effective customer relationships by strategically working on a unified and consistent set of communications tools for a company or product. It is essential in creating an integrated and cohesive marketing plan and developing successful marketing strategies for a company.

Social media and digital marketing are tools that are of great importance to companies today. They help companies develop customer interactions, build brand relationships, sell products and services, improve customer relationships, and create a safe and simple communication environment with the communication intentions adopted by the company. The role of social media and digital marketing is significant in the following areas:

Building customer relationships: Social media and digital marketing play a huge role in building customer relationships for companies. They provide users with the opportunity to connect in real and personal spaces and help build a good relationship with them.

Brand Awareness: Social media and digital marketing play a major role in building brand identity and increasing brand awareness. They help to strengthen the connection between customers and the brand by changing the brand image, conveying the brand's history, and demonstrating brand values.

Selling products and services: Social media and digital marketing are important tools for companies to sell products and services, helping them connect with customers by showing users about the company's products and services, offering discounts, and rebates.

Improve customer relationships: Social media and digital marketing play a big role in building better customer relationships for companies. They help build trust in the company by establishing initial connections with customers, welcoming them, and accepting their feedback.

In general, to build and strengthen customer relationships in marketing, a company must understand its customers well, provide superior service, use digital tools, and implement customer loyalty programs. Through this process, the company will increase customer loyalty and succeed in the market.

Today, the plant includes the following workshops:

1. Electric steel melting shop;
2. Roll forming shop;
3. Zoldir rolling shop;
4. Non-ferrous metals production workshop;
5. Heat-resistant materials production workshop;
6. Consumer goods production workshop;
7. Workshops for the preparation and processing of ferrous metal scrap and waste throughout the republic;
8. Branches of the "Secondary Nonferrous Metals" Department of "Uzmetkombinat" JSC;
9. Ferroalloy production workshop.

Table 1.

Actual production volume (tons) for the following years

Shop name	2016	2017	2018	2019	2022	2023
ESPC (steel)	654.7	660.7	911.2	950.1	950.0	1000.5
SPTs-1 (pomolnye shary)	185.0	195.1	235.2	188.1	183.4	180.7
СIII-1 (variety)	6.0	6.7	6.2	14.0	7.6	9.0
SPC-2 (variety)	522.7	520.8	809.3	855.0	899.0	740.6
StPC (wire)	10.3	10.8	10.0	10.6	10.1	23.0
PTsM (non-ferrous metals)	0.8	0.8	1.0	1.3	1.5	2.0
PTIM (basalt)	8.7	8.5	7.4	12.2	11.2	6.5
TsPF (Ferrosplavy)	-	-	3.9	17.2	25.1	28.1

PTNP (emelirovannaya posuda)	2.2	2.4	2.7	1.7	2.8	8.5
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From the table above, we can understand that the products and their quantities produced in all workshops between 2016 and 2023. The demand for enamelware alone has increased by 200% year on year, and the volume of production has grown by 200%. If in 2016 the production volume was 2.2 thousand tons, then by 2023 this figure will be 8.5 thousand tons.

The composition of the goods produced by Uzmetkombinat JSC:

- Armature
- Circle
- Rectangle
- My tongue
- Corner
- Shweller
- Hexagonal
- Steel rods

**Figure 2. Ferrous metal rolling
Thermal insulation materials.**

	Tank (16.0; 32.0 l)
	Can (2.0; 3.0; 0.6 l)

	<p>Saucepan (1.5; 4.5 l)</p>
	<p>Bucket (12.0 l)</p>
	<p>Casserole with stainless rim (1.5; 3.5l)</p>
	<p>Cylindrical pan (1.5; 2.5; 3.0; 3.5; 5.5; 7.0; 12.0 l)</p>
	<p>Spherical saucepan (2.5 l)</p>

We can clearly see that the 4Ps, which are elements of the Marketing mix, are working at the combine. According to them, the marketing concept of improving the product is followed first. That is, special importance is given to improving the consumer properties of the product. The main focus is on highest quality. The main focus is on the product, and therefore marketing actions affect the quality of the goods, or rather, its modernization. This corresponds to the product in the 4P elements.

If sufficient, even aggressive, efforts are not made in the field of product promotion, sales and sales promotion, consumers will not buy the company's goods in the required quantities. Many

companies resort to this concept when they encounter difficulties in sales and signs of overproduction begin to appear. The goal of such companies and firms is not to produce goods that the market demands, but to sell the goods they have produced. Accordingly, the plant enters the world market by exporting its products not only to the Uzbek market, but also to other developed countries. For example, these include the countries of Central Asia, Turkey, Azerbaijan, the Baltic states and a number of other European countries. As a result, the sales channels of the goods expand. However, according to the terms of almost all contracts, the plant undertakes to deliver them either to its borders or to the borders of the city of Bekabad.

In a row, the combine www.uzbeksteel.uz official website, social media "[Facebook](#)", "[Instagram](#)", "[Twitter](#)", "[Telegram](#)", "[YouTube](#)" It also maintains its pages based on the high standards and basic principles of professional journalism: objectivity, reliability, and neutrality!

In conclusion, the role of direct and event marketing at the plant is also invaluable. Uzmetkombinat actively participated in the recent exhibition in the field of "Black Metallurgy" held in Syrdarya with the People's Republic of China. These appearances at exhibitions and festivals present their products to almost the entire population through sponsorship programs. All of these represent the plant's communication channels. It produces a catalog representing the product range, improves it, and thus carries out advertising activities.

REFERENCES

1. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. 166 dated 29.03.2021.
2. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. The rule of law and the protection of human interests are the key to the country's development and the well-being of the people. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2017.- 48 p.
3. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. We will build a great future with our brave and noble people. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2017.- 488 p.
4. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. January 24, 2020. - People's Speech, January 26, 2020.
5. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 dated February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan".
6. 6.Azimovna, MS (2022). Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service, Samarkand, Uzbekistan. Formation of psychology and pedagogy as interdisciplinary sciences, 1(9), 20-23.
7. Musayeva, S., & Usmanov, F. (2022). Ways to develop marketing activities in tourist organizations. Science and innovation, 1(A5), 84-88.
8. 8.Azimovna, MS, Ilkhomovna, UD, & Shokhrukhovich, UF (2022). Issues of improving productivity competition in agriculture. Online scientific journal of innovation in social sciences.-2022.-C, 51-53.
9. 9.Azimovna, MS, Ilkhomovna, UD, & Shokhrukhovich, UF (2022). The role of marketing in increasing the economic efficiency of service enterprises.
10. 10.Azimovna, MS, Ilkhomovna, UD, & Shokhrukhovich, UF (2022). The concept of a correct marketing policy in trade and service enterprises.
11. Musayeva, S. (2022). Studying the organization of advertising activities of goods at "Samarkand tea packaging factory" JSC. Science and innovation, 1(A6), 185-192.
12. Musayeva, S. (2022). Prospects for the development of "stekloplastik" llc activity in the conditions of the market economy. Science and innovation, 1(A6), 539-546.

13. 13.Azimovna, MS, Ilkhomovna, UD, & Shokhrukhovich, UF (2022). Importance and Characteristics of Brand Choice in Services. *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science*, 1-3.
14. 14.Musaeva Sh. A. Marketing research. Textbook Publishing and creative department of "STAR-SEL" LLC. Samarkand–2023
15. Musaeva Sh. A. Integrated marketing communication. Textbook. "Mahorat" publishing house, Samarkand -2022.